

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY
BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING**

The 3rd meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held in Dean's Chamber of College of Physiotherapy, City campus, Pandeshwar on **05.03.2018**.

Members present were:-

- Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson) *SR*
Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member) *Ajay*
Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member) *Thrishala*
Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor (Member) *Annayya*
Dr. Prameela P. Hubli (Member) *Prameela*

Members not present were:-

- Dr. Padmakumar (External Member) **ABSENT**
Dr. Rakesh Krishna Kovala (External Member) **ABSENT**

In the beginning of the meeting the Chairman of the BOS welcomed all the members. After that the BOS discussed and resolved the following items:

- 1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 09.10.2017.**
 - The minutes of the BOS meeting held on 9th October 2017 were circulated among the BOS members. Since no comment has been received, this BOS has approved the minutes of the BOS meeting.

- 2. Introduction of Choice Based Credit System (CBCS) in BPT syllabus from the Academic year 2018-19.**
 - Dr. S. Rajasekar proposed that the CBCS system needs to be introduced from the year 2018 onwards in the BPT programme and this proposal was seconded by Dr. Thrishala Noronha.
 - Resolution:** The BOS discussed the item and approved the new syllabus of BPT Course (2018 batch) which was designed as per CBCS system and resolved to recommend to the Academic Council for approval.

3. Preparation of question bank for I semester BPT (2018 batch).

- Dr. S. Rajasekar proposed that the question bank for the I semester BPT (2018 batch) needs to be prepared.

-Resolution: All members discussed and resolved that the question bank for I semester BPT (2018 batch) will be prepared by the respective faculty and submitted to the Dean by May 31st 2018. The compilation would be done by the librarians.

4. Planning the academic calendar for Odd semesters of BPT for the period of June to December 2018.

-Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar requested that the academic calendar for the odd semesters of BPT and MPT be planned for the year 2018-19 (June- December 2018).

-Resolution: The members discussed and structured the academic calendar for the odd semesters of BPT and MPT and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval.

5. Formation of Board of examiners for BPT and MPT programmes.

The Chairperson explained the criteria related to the selection of BOE members and requested the Board to suggest names.

-Resolution: The Board prepared the list of BOE members in the Physiotherapy programmes for the academic year 2018-19 and resolved to recommend the same to the University.

6. Introduction of Value added courses for BPT and MPT for the year 2018-19.

Chairperson explained the requirement for adding value added course (not a part of curriculum) for BPT and MPT programmes.

-Resolution: The board discussed on this matter and it was decided that,

- for BPT 1st year- Basic Nursing and First Aid; BPT 2nd year- Diet and Nutrition
- for MPT 1st year- Basic Life Support; MPT 2nd year- Yoga

The meeting started at 9.30 am and went on till 12.00 pm

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
BOS, College of Physiotherapy

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

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The 4th meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held at in Dean chamber of College of Physiotherapy, Pandeshwar on **02.11.2018**.

Members present were:

- Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson) *SR*
Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member) *Ajay*
Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member) *Thrishala*
Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor (Member) *Annayya*
Dr. Rakesh Krishna Kovela (External Member) *Rakesh*

Members not present were:

- Dr. Padmakumar (External Member) **ABSENT**
Dr. Prameela P. Hubli (Member) **ABSENT**

The Chairman welcomed all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting thereafter deliberated on agenda items:

1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 05.03.2018.

-The minutes of the meeting held on 5th March 2018 were read and confirmed unanimously by all the members.

2. Preparation of question bank for II semester BPT (2018 batch).

- Dr. S. Rajasekar proposed that the question bank for the II semester BPT (2018 batch) needs to be prepared.

-Resolution: All members discussed and resolved that the question bank for 2nd semester BPT (2018 batch) will be prepared by the respective faculty and submitted to the Dean by February 10th 2019. The compilation would be done by the librarians.

3. Planning the academic calendar for even semesters of BPT for the period of December 2018-April 2019.

-Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar requested that the academic calendar for the even semesters of BPT and MPT be planned for the year 2018-19 (December 2018-April 2019).

-Resolution: The members discussed and structured the academic calendar for the academic year 2019-20 of even semesters of BPT and MPT and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval.

4. Preparation of Panel of examiners/gradation list.

The Chairperson requested the Board members to prepare the panel of examiners for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th semester end examination of BPT programme.

-Resolution: The Board members prepared the panel of examiners for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th semester end examination of BPT and resolved to recommend the same to the University and send the panel of examiners list in a sealed cover to Registrar (Evaluation).

The meeting started at 9.30 am and ended at 11.00 am with thanks to the Chair.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
BOS, College of Physiotherapy

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